

Empowerment of Farm Women in Tirunelveli District-A Study

Dr. P. Mary Thangam

Assistant Professor

Department of Economics & Research Centre

Sarah Tucker College Tirunelveli

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Mary Thangam, P.

“Empowerment of Farm Women in Tirunelveli District-A Study.”

Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 34–38.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549236>

The issue of women empowerment is a little complex and multidimensional. Besides, providing rights and creating awareness does not solve the problem of women. The development programs and policies, which aim at women empowerment, should categorize women based on their age, caste, class, region, education, etc. as they are not a homogeneous group which aims at empowerment.

For more than a decade in India, the term ‘empowerment’ had been widely used about women. The Eighth Five Year plan gave greater emphasis on women as equal partners and participants in the development process and thereby conceptual thinking shifted from development to empowerment of farm women. Empowerment is about power and described as control resources and ideology. Women in general and poor women, in particular, are powerless because they do not have any of these controls.

Empowerment of Women and Watershed Development Programs

In recent years the Government of India has adopted a ‘watershed development approach’ to reverse the degradation of these lands and thereby increase productivity and provide wage employment. “The government would endeavor to give a joint title to husband and wife in the development activities involving the transfer of assets. This would be taken up for implementation to start within programs like distribution of land and house sites and beneficiary oriented economic units”.

Watershed development has been adopted in India to address land degradation and the need for agricultural productivity. Women has tended to be marginalized in watershed development projects because of the focus on land development, which has given the control of land in many parts of India, makes it male-focused. Women are often left out of such projects matters, because women play a central role in management of natural resources. Land-based activities usually generate more income and carry less risk than non-land based activities that women are often encouraged to take up.

And hence Empowerment of Women may be focused in its Dimensional aspects like:

- Education
- Training
- Employment

Education

‘To awaken people, it is the woman who has to be awakened, once she moves, the country moves and thus we build India tomorrow.’

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

Training

Training is influence the operational behavior of millions of persons in the world in their respective vocations. The purpose of training is to achieve a change in the behavior of those been trained. The training aims to increase interpersonal effectiveness, allowing an individual to work better with other people.

Employment

Employment provides income and thereby leads to economic independence and decision-making power of women. Household production is a important user of time and labor of women which contributes significantly to the well-being of the household. Employment of women in organized and unorganized sectors has drawn a large number of women out of the family who make their contribution to the economy visible. The women are playing a crucial role in agriculture and allied activities. More than 65 percent of women in these countries are engaged in agriculture and only 16-17 percent in industry or services, while far-reaching structural changes have taken place in the developed countries with the shift of female labor force away from agricultural and industrial occupations to the services sector.

Statement of the Problem

Nearly all over the world it is quite natural that a woman was considered a cornered group; they are not able to access the resources which are essential for development. About 80 percent of all economically active women in India are engaged in agriculture, they work longer and harder than men. Usually, the low income, low skilled, and minimum productivity jobs are female-specific. It is quite obvious that women constitute nearly half of the nation’s population; they have tremendous latent potential to contribute to harnessing technology for human and social development. Primarily rural women are means of survival of their families but are generally unrecognized and placed at the bottom. They have lesser access to assets, resources, opportunities, and credit. It is recollected that the Indian constitution, in its fundamental rights, has provisions for equality, social justice, and protection for women.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the current socio-economic status of farm women in the study area.
- To compare the status of farm women before and after the watershed program in the study area.

Methods and materials

The present study is different attempt to scrutinize the empowerment of farm women in Tirunelveli District. As the this attempted to assess the empowerment of farm women particularly those who are involved in the watershed development programs in Tirunelveli District, to observe

the data from the respondents Random Sampling Method have been administered and the ultimate sample size is 400 farm women. There are 238, 4370, 4750 and 751 women in the four watersheds selected as Petteri, Melacheval, Madathupatti, and Chelianallur respectively. From this total population of 9358, a sample of 400 farm women beneficiaries was selected. Some statistical tools, like mean difference, Percentage correlation, trend analysis, and ANOVA, have been used to touch the objectives. The study collects both primary and secondary data. Primary has been collected for the period 2009 and 2010. And the secondary data have been collected for 10 years 2008-2018.

Empowerment of Women

The following aspects lead to the empowerment of women:

- Recognizing women’s contribution and women’s knowledge
- Women are enhancing their self-respect and self -dignity.
- Women are controlling their bodies.
- Women are becoming economically independent and self- reliant.

Women in the Farm Sector

Govind (2016) says that A higher percentage of women was engaged in farm operations like seed treatment, sowing, manure, inter-cultivation, harvest and post-harvest technology that were traditionally done by women in all livestock activities was more compared to their involvement in crop husbandry practices.

Occupation

Occupation plays a decisive role in one’s progress. The sample respondents are classified into small farmer’s marginal farmers, agricultural coolies, and bonded laborers broadly. Details is presented in the following table

Table 1 Caste wise Distribution of Sample respondents by Occupation

Occupation of the sample respondents					
	Small farmers	Marginal farmer	Agricultural cooly	Bonded labor	Total
BC	93	4	149	13	259
	(35.9)	(1.5)	(57.5)	(5.0)	(100)
MBC	16	35	6	33	90
	(17.8)	(38.9)	(6.7)	(36.7)	(100)
SC/ST	0	32	19	0	51
	(0)	(62.7)	(37.3)	(0)	(100)
Total	109	71	174	46	400
	(27.3)	(17.8)	(43.5)	(11.5)	(100)

(Figures in the parentheses indicate the percentage to respective totals)Source: Computed from primary data

It was observed that a maximum 43.5 percent are agricultural coolies followed by 27.3 percent small farmers; 17.8 percent marginal farmers and 11.5 percent bonded laborers respectively. The last variable is the least. There are neither small farmers nor bonded laborers among the SC/STs. BC small farmers claim 35.9 percent, and their cooly size is 57.5 percent. The highest bonded labor percentage was found in the MBC group.

Level of Technical Knowledge of Farm Women

A knowledgeable person is capable of clear and balanced thinking. He can take the right decisions at the appropriate time. This scheme under study enriches farm women with knowledge by way of different extension strategies. It is therefore hypothesized that the beneficiary farm women with a higher level of knowledge about agriculture, are likely to participate more in decision-making process and are also better empowered.

$$\text{Knowledge Index} = \frac{\text{Knowledge score for all correct answers}}{\text{Maximum possible knowledge score} \div \text{respondents from women}} \times 100$$

Based on score earned, a farm woman was categorized into the following three groups;

- (a) Farm women with low knowledge: Knowledge Index up to 12
- (b) Farm women with medium knowledge: Knowledge Index between 14 to 18
- (c) Farm women with high knowledge: Knowledge Index 18 & above

The farm women was classified into the following categories according to the score of Decision Making Index

- Low decision Making----- score up 12
- Medium Decision making----- score up 14 to 30
- High Decision making-----Score 20 and above

Farm women with no enrichment in decision –making through the above consider 12 factors were given zero scores. If is enriched with just participation through 12 factors, one score was given. And the experience gained, and the knowledge acquires through the above mentioned 12 factors were carried out.

Decision Making Index (Before)

Low Decision Making	-	213
Medium Decision Making	-	98
High Decision Making	-	89

Decision Making Index (After)

Less Decision Making	-	165
Medium Decision Making	-	132
High Decision Making	-	103

The Karl Pearsons Coefficient of Correlation formula (Gupta,1997) was employed to find out the correlation between the socio- economic factors and decision making, which is as under:

The t- test is used to test the significance of an observed correlation coefficient (Gupta, 1997).

When,

n= no. Of observations and k = parameter, but here k=2.

Conclusion

There is a need to ensure that women do not become overwhelmed by schemes and programs focused at them and are not persuaded to participate simply for short-term incentives (wage labor), but can make informed choices about what is best for them and their families. That remains the big

challenge. The empowerment of women through activities that bring them sustainable economic independence and provide them with a 'voice' can help to shift the socio-economic cultural and political norms which prevent the effective implementation of legislation which supports their right to land and property and the status that goes with those rights. Economic independence of women would accelerate the improvement of the women. Government would endeavor to give a joint title to husband and wife in the development activities involving the transfer of assets.

References

1. Anonymous, (2005) Background paper on Technology Dissemination for women in Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture, Govt. of. India. p.4.
2. Govind. S., (2016) "Participation of farm women in farm and Home Activities," *Kurukshetra* 22 (4): 18-22.
3. Lipi Das and S.K Mishra (2006) Decent work and empowerment of women in Agriculture, *Kurukshetra*, May vol.XXI, p.42.
4. Subashini. R., (2000) Role of farm women in Agriculture *Indian Journal of Home Science* 5(1): 27-29.
5. Patel A.R., (2007) Women in Agricultural Production, RDA Challenging Task for Voluntary Agencies, New Delhi, pp. 8-10.